

Cascadia Region Earthquake Science Center

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Placing quantitative bounds on the use of
paleo-landslide distributions as
paleo-earthquake indicators along the
Cascadia margin

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Final Report: Placing quantitative bounds on the use of paleo-landslide distributions as paleoearthquake indicators along the Cascadia margin

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1. Introduction

The purpose of this project was to characterize the effects of age uncertainties and preservation bias in the geomorphic record of deep-seated landslides over Holocene time scales. Landslide clusters in space or time, as well as individual dated landslides, are often used as paleoseismic indicators (Jibson, 1996; Black et al., 2023), but the reliability of such records has not been systematically analyzed. Approximate dating of hundreds to thousands of landslides throughout the Pacific Northwest has suggested little clear influence of known paleoearthquakes, either from the Cascadia Subduction Zone (CSZ) or local crustal faults (LaHusen et al., 2016; 2020; Booth et al., 2017), with the exception of the Seattle Fault (Herzig et al., 2023) and Boulder Creek Fault (Underwood et al., *accepted*) in Washington. This does not necessarily indicate that paleoearthquakes did not trigger many landslides, but may instead suggest that high age uncertainties and preservation bias due to younger landslides overprinting older ones obscured the signal of paleoearthquakes. As such, this project developed and applied a spatially explicit statistical model to answer a basic question: When is an apparent cluster of paleo-landslides a reliable indicator of a paleoearthquake?

2. Key results

We developed the statistical model and calibrated its parameters based on previously documented landslide size distributions and age uncertainties in western Washington (Fig. 1; Booth et al., 2017; Herzig et al., 2023). Example model outputs for a low, medium, and high imposed steady background landslide frequency are shown in Fig. 2. When frequency is low, landslides rarely overprint one another, and the observed landslide frequency exhibits random variability over time, centered around the imposed rate. At a medium frequency, some landslides overprint others, which generates a preservation bias, such that the apparent landslide frequency exponentially decays with age to about half its true value over the Holocene. At the high landslide frequency, preservation bias is widespread, and almost no landslides older than about 5 ky are even detectable at present. Based on the shape of observed frequency v. age curves, most landslide-prone areas of the Pacific Northwest correspond to the medium to high examples shown here.

If landslide ages are known exactly, preservation bias first becomes detectable at an imposed frequency of $0.006 \text{ km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$, which is less than typically documented landslide frequencies in many susceptible regions, suggesting preservation bias should be an issue in many landslide records. However, knowing the exact ages of all landslides in a region is obviously not feasible, and when uncertainties in landslide age are introduced to the statistical model, actual preservation bias is compounded by an apparent preservation bias that occurs at lower landslide frequencies and also becomes more pronounced at higher frequencies. We hypothesized that

Figure 1. Statistical model inputs including: (a) Probability distribution of landslide deposit areas in the North Fork Stillaguamish River valley (Booth et al., 2017), fit with an inverse gamma distribution; and (b) Landslide age-roughness model for North Fork Stillaguamish and Seattle region landslides from Herzig et al. (2024), shown as the solid line, with normally-distributed random relative errors added to the roughness shown as shaded points.

Figure 2. Examples of statistical model outputs for three representative imposed landslide frequencies of 0.001, 0.01, and 0.1 $\text{landslides km}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$, with each column of the figure corresponding to a different frequency. (a-c) Mapview of an 8 by 10 km model domain with landslides colored according to their age, and no landslides shown as white background. (d-f) Number-based landslide frequency v. age as observed at the end of the model run in 200-yr bins (solid black lines) and as imposed and averaged over the entire 12,400-yr model run (solid red line). (g-i) Areal landslide frequency v. age with lines colored as in (d-f).

these effects would obscure potential clusters of landslides in time, which we tested by imposing landslide “pulses” with different magnitudes at different times on top of a steady background rate in each model run.

The two primary controls on whether a landslide pulse is detectable are the size of the landslide pulse and the age at which the pulse occurred (Fig. 3). We defined pulse magnitude as the equivalent number of years required at the background landslide rate to generate the number of landslides in the pulse. A pulse was deemed detectable if landslide frequency at that time exceeded the 95% prediction interval of an exponential fit to the frequency v. age plot observed at the end of the model run. Assuming landslide ages are known exactly, which is not reasonable for the real world, but allows us to see the fundamental behavior, pulse magnitude is the primary control on whether it is statistically detectable (Fig. 3a). However, as landslide frequency increases and preservation bias plays more of a role, the age of the pulse becomes increasingly important, with older pulses requiring larger magnitudes to be detected. When a moderate age uncertainty is imposed, both pulse magnitude and age are important controls on detectability, and detection thresholds are more restrictive (Fig. 3b). For large age uncertainties, pulse magnitude plays almost no role, and instead the pulse must be quite young for any hope of successful detection (Fig. 3c). Considering landslide areal frequency rather than number-based frequency introduces notable variability to these thresholds (Fig. 3d-f).

Figure 3. Best-fit detection thresholds for a landslide pulse in terms of pulse magnitude and pulse age for a range of landslide frequencies (colored lines). Detection thresholds were determined from number-based landslide frequency (top row, (a-c)), or area-based landslide frequency (bottom row, (d-f)). Left column (a and d) assumed exact landslide ages ($r_{std} = 0$), center column (b and e) imposed 10% relative roughness uncertainties ($r_{std} = 0.1$), and right column (c and f) imposed 25% relative roughness uncertainties ($r_{std} = 0.25$).

These thresholds performed well in terms of precision (89%, 76%, and 70% for no, moderate, and high age uncertainty, respectively, and number-based landslide frequency) across all frequencies. This suggests that false positives, when a peak in landslide frequency due only to random noise is statistically detected, should be relatively rare. On the other hand, recall was worse (87%, 53%, and 47%), suggesting that false negatives, where a pulse of landslides that is known to have occurred is not statistically detected, are more problematic.

Overall, the thresholds presented in Fig. 3 should serve as general guidelines for interpreting a landslide frequency v. age curve to infer whether or not paleolandslides likely correspond to paleoearthquakes. The relative roughness uncertainties of 10% and 25% presented here roughly correspond to qualitatively “good” and “bad” age-roughness models used to infer landslide ages in previous work. So once an age-roughness model for a study area is defined, one can estimate background landslide frequency and then estimate the size and timing of earthquake-triggered landslide events that should theoretically be detectable. For example, if a moderate landslide frequency of ~ 0.01 landslides $\text{km}^{-2} \text{yr}^{-1}$ is estimated from a “good” age-roughness model, Fig. 3b indicates that a very large event with a ~ 1000 -yr magnitude should be detectable up to about 5,000 yrs ago, while a smaller event with a ~ 200 -yr magnitude would likely be detected only close to the present (or more generally any combination of magnitude and age that exceeds the detection threshold). Similarly, if one finds a statistically significant pulse in landslide frequency at a specific time, a minimum landslide event magnitude can be inferred. Many crustal faults in Cascadia are known to have ruptured in the past several thousand years based on paleoseismic work, and our modeling results suggest that those paleoearthquakes are plausibly detectable in the present-day landslide record if they triggered landslide events with magnitudes on the order of hundreds of years.

In summary, this project sought to answer three main research questions: (1) What are the expected “background” distributions of landslide sizes and ages preserved in a landscape without earthquakes?; (2) What size trigger is required to create a statistically detectable peak in the landslide age distribution, and how does this change with time since the triggering event?; and (3) Can we confidently identify landslides triggered by CSZ or crustal fault earthquakes from the geomorphic record observable at present? Key results that we highlighted above largely accomplished these goals. Generally, we found the following: (1) Background distributions of landslide frequency as a function of time exhibit an increasing degree of preservation bias as that background frequency increases; (2) Assuming realistic age uncertainties and background landslide frequencies for the Pacific Northwest, detectable landslide event size increases systematically with event age from order 10 to 100 year event magnitude in the recent past to order 1000 yr event magnitude a few thousand years ago; and therefore (3) it is indeed likely possible to identify clusters of earthquake-triggered paleolandslides in Cascadia based on the event magnitude-age thresholds defined above. To maximize the potential identifying such clusters, landslide age uncertainties should be as small as possible, and number-based landslide frequency should be more reliable than area-based frequency.

One main aspect of this study that we chose to tackle differently than in the original proposal was the type of numerical modeling carried out. The proposal planned on using a process-based numerical landscape evolution model with simplified, physics-based rules governing a suite of geomorphic processes. After running the landscape evolution model a few times, we realized its

numerous free parameters and their combined direct and indirect effects on landslide frequency actually hindered answering our fundamental research questions. Additionally, large variability among model runs that used the same parameters suggested that we would need to carry out thousands of runs, which would take an unreasonable amount of time. So instead, we developed a new, faster, spatially explicit statistical model from scratch and designed it in a way that would give us direct control over the independent variables of interest, most importantly the landslide size distribution, frequency, and pulse magnitude. This allowed us to carry out the thousands of runs necessary to capture average trends and their variability and to directly connect fundamental model outputs to their controlling factors. As in any modeling study, it's important to define a model that is best suited to answering the research questions of the project.

3. Future work

We have drafted a manuscript that reports in detail the results summarized above and plan to submit it to *Journal of Geophysical Research-Earth Surface* in the upcoming 2025-26 academic year. We also plan to present results at one or more national meetings over that same time frame, such as the annual Geological Society of America Cordilleran section meeting or Community Surface Dynamics Modeling System annual meeting. To finalize the study for the manuscript and meetings, we will add a section in which we reanalyze and interpret previously published landslide frequency histories in the context of our new model.

Results of the present study suggest several avenues for future development of related projects. First, since age uncertainty introduces an apparent preservation bias and makes landslide pulse detection thresholds more restrictive, effort should be focused on improving methods for dating large numbers of landslides. Previous work has used standard regression of landslide age against average landslide deposit roughness to estimate landslide ages with considerable uncertainty. However, age is likely not the only independent variable that affects roughness, and more complex statistical techniques that include factors such as landslide size, shape, and type; multiple ways of quantifying roughness and other topographic derivatives; and contextual data like climate, lithology, and land-use could refine age estimates. Second, since precise ages (e.g. accurate to the year) of large numbers of landslides are likely not attainable, indicators of earthquake-triggered landslides beyond just their timing should be developed. These could include systematic morphological or topographic position differences between earthquake-triggered landslides and those triggered by other factors such as elevated pore water pressures or baselevel lowering. Last, although the statistical model we chose to use in this study let us effectively answer our basic research questions, it would still be useful to use a full landscape evolution model to tailor results to specific study areas and infer what processes most drive real and apparent changes in landslide frequency over time.